

EDITORIAL ARTICLE

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The European Society of Surgery (ESS) was established almost thirty years ago, in the 20th century. In the same year, Great Britain transferred sovereignty of Hong Kong to China, European Union consisted of 15 countries, the first edition of “Harry Potter and the Philosopher’s Stone” was released.

Luc Arthur Michel our first General Secretary wrote « that our goal was to build bridges between surgical communities in Europe and beyond, and to enable the exchange of surgical knowledge.

Time passed, some other international surgical societies vanished, but our society remained. This is thanks to the enthusiastic and hard-working members who have been supporting the Society in many ways. In 2026, we decided to open a new scientific journal, which will publish papers from all surgical disciplines. We hope that JESS will serve for many years as a source of knowledge for medical community.

The initiative came early on in 2026 from the ESS President Dr. Vinod K. Singhal and our members from Dubai. Abruptly, a new war came making the future more obscure.

Even in these difficult times, as after the fall of the Berlin Wall, the ESS goal is to continue facilitating the exchange of ideas and expertises. Medicine, medical knowledge and research should help people and should be accessible for all who need it.

This is why we do invite all surgeons to join the ESS members by publishing their opinions and scientific achievements in the JESS.

Editor in Chief
Antoni M. Szczepanik MD. PhD FEBS.

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